

The Saga of the Faerie Queene - The use of Epic Conventions in Edmund Spenser's Allegorical Tale

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 8

Special Issue: 1

Month: December

Year: 2019

P-ISSN: 2320-2645

E-ISSN: 2582-3531

Impact Factor: 4.110

Citation:

Vinothkumar, G. "The Saga of the Faerie Queene - The Use of Epic Conventions in Edmund Spenser's Allegorical Tale."

Shanlax International Journal of English, vol. 8, no. S1, 2019, pp. 1–3.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3599826>

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Introduction

Through this paper I will try to explain in what ways Edmund Spenser's poem *The Faerie Queene* can be defined as an epic. In *The Faerie Queene* this is no different: by wielding the typical characteristics of the genre of the epic Spenser works in the tradition of both classical and medieval epic writers such as respectively Homer and Virgil, and Ariosto and Tasso. There are two kinds of epic conventions: the textual-related and the content-related (and some conventions that overlap these two distinct domains of text and content). By using this division, I will deal with the textual-related first and subsequently with the context-related conventions, describing the general concepts of the characteristic and at the same time indicating where and how Spenser applies and integrates it in his magnificent epic poem, for epic it is and there will be no doubt about that at the end of this paper.

Five Conventions

Generally five epic conventions are there in the text of the epic.

1. A first one concerns the way an epic text commences: in medias res (Lat. "into the middle of things"). This is a narrative technique which plunges the reader straight into the middle of the story, rather than at the beginning the story by flashbacks. Spenser even mentions explicitly in the prefatory letter to Sir Walter Raleigh that he uses this epic convention ("(...) but a poet thrust into the midst (...)") and that the true beginning of the story is told in book XII (which is, unfortunately, not written).
2. The invocation of the Muse at the beginning of an epic poem. The Muse of epic poetry, the reference is to Clio, the Muse of history, or to Calliope, the latter seeming the most probable.
3. Epic similes, also called Homeric simile, are a third textual epic convention. They involve long, elaborate, ornate, detailed and complex comparisons – usually between a character and

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his environment – used to make vivid an image and to describe or clarify. There are many examples of this convention in *The Faerie Queene*.

4. While Spenser's poem is completely written in an elevated tone, we can find a lot of examples of these speeches by characters.
5. The Knight of the Redcrosse is among others named "the Champion (stout)", "the valiant Elfe", "the Elfin knight while Una is often referred to as "that Ladie milde" or "faithful Dame".

Text and content

Between the textual and content-related epic conventions there is a cross-cutting zone of two characteristics which can both be related to text and content. The first is the use of the epic catalog or a long list of items. This can be an enumeration of several objects of the same class, but can also be a genealogy. The first catalog we encounter in *The Faerie Queene* is the list of trees in stanzas 8 and 9 of Book I. Still in Book I there is a list of armour given and, in Canto V, stanzas 47-50, a list of the men and women whose bodies lie in the dungeon of the House of pride. In Book II there chronicle of Faeries, a catalog of sea monsters and a chronicle of the line of the Briton kings. In Book II there is a genealogic part which shows that Elizabeth I comes forth from the line of King Arthur, thus adding yet another element of glorification of the queen to his epic.

Theme

The second cross-cutting epic convention is the statement of the theme. We find this at the beginning of every canto in Spenser's epic poem: the canto commences with a four-line sentence, stating briefly what is about to happen, thus reducing the surprising element-which I find is rather a pity, as you already know what is going to happen. Fortunately, the magnificent poetic skills of Spenser and his incredible way of telling compensate for this small matter.

Content Related Characteristics

The main character of the story, is always human-not a god or whatsoever he possesses some supernatural powers or qualities particular civilization and is in regards a national hero.

1. At the end of his quest, there always awaits the hero a reward, be it a treasure, inheritance or high position, and he returns home transformed (in a positive way) if we apply this concept of the hero to Spenser's *The Faerie Queene*, then it is not difficult at all to find these matters. I will take Book I as example, which is in itself already a miniature epic.
2. The Redcrosse, knight though at first said to be an Elven knight, is later on identified as Saint George, the patron saint of England turning him human and national hero at the same time, confirming the generic conventions of the epic a fortiori. His more or less supernatural powers are shown in various battles: the fight with Error.
3. A next epic convention in terms of content is the intervention in human affairs by gods, most frequently in classical epic tradition, or supernatural forces, in medieval epic tradition. In *The Faerie Queene* there are quite some examples of this convention to be found first example, the noble knight is about to kill Sansjoy, when the latter suddenly disappears in a black cloud. The sudden appearance of the well and the tree is no coincidence at all: they are set there by supernatural forces who intervene in the battle between the knight and the beast.
4. A third epic convention concerning is the vast setting of the story, and, related to this, the journey to the underworld (e.g. the descent into hell by Aencis, in *The Aeneid* by Virgil). The setting covers great geographical distances and often, the story takes place in another world, a fictional place, which is no different in *The Faerie Queene*: the story is set in Faerie Land and great distances are bridged like Duessa's journey into hell with Night to retrieve Sansjoy.

5. The last epic convention is the describing of the arming or the armour of the hero. Examples of this convention is Spenser's poem can be found at the beginning of the first canto, where the armour of Redcrosse is described.

Spenser wants to be both modern and ancient, but the legacy left behind him has proven that despite his efforts, he could not have it both ways. Jonson, who wrote in the age following Spenser's death, where his influence would have been at its most fresh, regarded him not as a contemporary who was advancing poetic technique and thought, but as an ancient who is to be honored (Alpers, 2001, 255). Thus in the early 17th century, Spenser had already assumed the status of the revered ancient poet, with the company of those such as Chaucer, rather than Marlowe or Shakespeare. His reliance on imitation and allusion created a work with too little to offer in the way of original characters and situations, relying on long-establishment forms and archetypal circumstances for his matter, of which his indebtedness to past traditions made him a part of England literary past, instead of a contributing member of England literary future.

Spenser is effectively created a complex system of interpretation and meaning within his epic, where the dreamlike realm of Faerie Land, projects a reality of its own. It is a product of the poet's imagination, only inhibited by the verse form he has chosen, where the grand epic is seen side with sensual scenes taken from a deep well of mythology and Biblical lore. Focusing too much on Spenser's intention regarding the allegory which encapsulates the epic largely limits the complexity and scope of the poem. The key feature of Spenser's technique lies within the unique way in which Elizabethan poets regarded tradition and imitation of key figures within that framework.

All these characteristics of the epic genre can be found in the works by Homer (*Iliad*, *Odyssey*) and Virgil, and more 'recently' in the works by the Italians Ariosto (*Orlando furioso*) and Tasso (*Jerusalem Delivered*). These epic poets all had direct textual and content-related influence on Spenser which is clearly visible in *The Faerie Queene*. Although these 'influences' could now be seen as plagiarism, this was not at all the case in Spenser's time. On the contrary, it was considered a sign of the well-educated poet, who has knowledge of and uses different sources and styles to construct an even better epic.

Conclusion

To conclude, it is appropriate to say that there rests no more doubt about it that Edmund Spenser's magnificent poem is an epic in both text and content. Spenser has skillfully adopted the traditional epic conventions wielded by his famous predecessors and applied them to his own poem, creating one of the better representatives-if not the best representative-of the epic genre in the post-classical age and hereby deserving his place among such Giants of epic poetry as Homer, Virgil, Dante, Ariosto and Tasso.

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